

EFFECTIVE METHODS AND TOOLS FOR ELIMINATING MORPHOLOGICAL AND SYNTACTIC ERRORS IN SPEECH

D.Teshaboyev

Doctor of Philological Sciences (DSc), FarDU

D. Jo'raqozieva

Master's Student, FarDU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15632148>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 01-June 2025 yil

Ma'qullandi: 07-June 2025 yil

Nashr qilindi: 10-June 2025 yil

KEY WORDS

morphological, syntactic, speech errors, method, technique, primary school student, textbook, approach, clarity, correctness, expressiveness, impact.

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the effective methods and tools for eliminating morphological and syntactic errors in the speech of primary school students. It outlines methods for enriching students' speech based on their age characteristics.

Analyzing speech errors found in students' activities, classifying them, identifying their types, and understanding the reasons behind them allow for the development of a systematic approach to their correction and prevention. This process involves:

- a) Correcting the speech errors found in students' notebooks;
- b) Addressing speech errors common to the whole class during lesson time. About 15–20 minutes of the lesson is dedicated to analyzing texts and allowing students to identify and correct errors themselves;
- c) Working on individual errors found in specific students during extracurricular time, with explanation of causes;
- d) Developing a system of methodological exercises aimed at preventing speech errors. Students are trained to work with errors by analyzing texts linguistically during reading and grammar classes;
- e) Before writing essays, narratives, or stories, students should practice lexical units and syntactic constructions commonly used in such texts, enabling them to express thoughts clearly and precisely;
- f) While learning grammar topics, it is necessary to explain how these topics help prevent speech errors;
- g) Teaching students to independently check and edit their own written work.

These approaches are especially appropriate for students in the 3rd and 4th grades. Correcting and preventing speech errors must be done in close connection with language work. It is essential to address students' oral and written mistakes in a timely manner. Each student should grasp the correct form and, if possible, understand the root cause of the error. The most effective method is allowing the student to correct their own mistakes.

If they are unable to do so, the teacher assists. Depending on the type of error,

corrections can be made in the following ways:

- restructuring the sentence or phrase;
- replacing the incorrect word with the correct one;
- adding necessary words into the text;
- crossing out unnecessary words.

In lessons dedicated to analyzing essays or narratives, about 20–25 minutes are spent working on errors. The teacher briefly summarizes student work, reads the best-written piece as a model, and then explains content, grammar, and speech mistakes, as well as how to correct them.

Some students demonstrate personal speech difficulties that must be addressed in special sessions held outside regular class hours. In such cases, one-on-one discussions are organized to help increase the student's mental engagement. The important part is that the child not only identifies the error but also learns how to correct and explain it.

For example, when studying the topic of "pronouns," showing students how personal pronouns can replace repeated words helps reinforce correct usage. This prepares students for coherent writing.

There are three main factors contributing to the successful development of students' speech:

- Attentive attitude toward language, interest in reading, and exposure to grammatically correct and expressive speech from people around them;
- How the student's speech experience is organized;
- The teacher's knowledge of linguistics, grammar, vocabulary, and stylistics.

In primary grades, students with speech deficiencies are commonly encountered. In such cases, teachers are expected not only to be knowledgeable but wise. These students should never be mocked or discriminated against. Usually, speech issues can be noticed early in Grade 1, though clearer identification comes with time.

For instance, a Grade 1 student named Fakhridin has difficulty pronouncing sounds like "r," "l," and "y." Embarrassed in front of classmates, he avoids words containing these sounds. A wise teacher notices this and begins working with him individually. Using toys, sweets, or pictures that contain the problematic sounds, the teacher asks simple questions like, "What is this, Fakhridin?" to encourage him to speak.

When the child responds with something like, "This is a tlaktol (tractor), teacher," his speech activity improves gradually and naturally. One-on-one sessions like these allow the child to express themselves freely without fear of being judged. Involving the child's parent—especially the mother—is also an important part of the process.

"Favorite Exercise" Method

To stimulate speech development at home, a child can be given their favorite treat – chocolate, jam, or cream – spread onto a small plate. The child then licks it with their tongue. This turns traditional speech therapy commands like "stick out your tongue, move it right, left, up, down" into a fun and engaging game.

This method helps detect phonetic articulation problems. Through cooperation between the speech therapist and teacher, the child's pronunciation can be significantly improved.

Key Requirements for Student Speech Development

1. Content Richness. A student's oral or written speech becomes rich and meaningful when based on life experiences, personal observations, books, pictures, radio, or TV programs. If a child speaks unprepared on a topic they don't understand, their speech sounds weak and meaningless.

2. Logical Structure. Thoughts must be expressed in a clear and logical order, avoiding repetition or off-topic ideas. Logical errors typically result from poor understanding or incorrect topic selection.

3. Clarity. It is crucial for students to express their thoughts in clear, simple language with accurate vocabulary and sentence structure.

4. Vocabulary Richness. To effectively convey meaning, a student needs a strong vocabulary. Though such a requirement is not strictly applied in lower grades, efforts should still be made to expand word knowledge.

5. Comprehensibility. Oral speech should be understandable to listeners, and written speech to readers. Tailoring speech to the age and interest of the audience increases effectiveness.

6. Expressiveness. Speech should be lively, vivid, and convincing. Oral speech relies on intonation, while written speech depends on word choice, emotional expression, and sentence variety.

7. Correctness. Students must adhere to the norms of literary language. This means observing grammar, spelling, punctuation in writing, and pronunciation norms in speaking.

These qualities are interrelated and must be applied collectively in the educational process.

Starting from primary education, children are taught to overcome deficiencies in their speech, to improve their oral language skills, and to express their thoughts coherently and systematically through free thinking about events they have seen or heard. They are also taught creative thinking because through speech, a person exchanges ideas and engages in communication. One of the most important characteristics of a person is their ability to speak. Thoughts expressed through fluent speech are understandable and pleasant. Speech is a unique and elevated form of communication that is exclusive to humans; during verbal communication, individuals exchange ideas and influence one another. Before correcting morphological errors in students' speech, it is necessary to enhance their morphological vocabulary. A student with sufficient vocabulary and knowledge on how to use those words will not make morphological mistakes.

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